

Nanoparticles as smart carriers to facilitate cancer immunotherapy

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Abstract

Cancer is classified under the heading of complex diseases; A disease in which a gene is not involved, does not have a specific cause, and multiple environmental, genetic, social, nutritional causes play a role in the development of cancer. Cancer treatment approaches include surgery, chemotherapy, radiotherapy and immunotherapy. the first three methods are invasive methods and there are many cases of cancer that do not respond to these treatments. In fact, immunotherapy is a manipulation of the immune system that introduces a new ability to the immune system and causes changes in the immune system; It either stimulates the immune system or blocks a pathway or activates a pathway. Cancer immunotherapy not only cures cancer by inducing strong anti-tumor immune responses, but also controls metastases and also prevents cancer recurrence, so it has major and important advantages over previous cancer treatments. Cancer treatment relying on the function of the immune system has gained a good position in recent years.

Keywords: Nanoparticles, Cancer, Immunotherapy, Smart Carriers.

1. Introduction

Immunotherapy is one of the most specific methods of tumor treatment that specifically destroys tumor cells and is performed in two ways:

1. Active immunotherapy:
 - A) Vaccines that containing DCs activated with tumor antigens.
 - B) Gene transferring of cytokines or co-stimulators.
 - C) non-specific stimulation of the immune system by using adjuvant.
2. Passive immunotherapy:
 - A) Tumor_infiltrating lymphocytes (TIL) therapy
 - B) Use of monoclonal antibodies

Review:

In immunotherapy, we need to know the tumor antigen. Tumor cells have two types of antigens, and our immune system can distinguish these cells from normal cells by these antigens:

1. Tumor specific antigens (TSA) which are only seen in cancer cells and cancerous tissues and are not seen in normal and healthy tissues at all and are the result of mutations on the structural part of genes and they are the result of qualitative changes in genes, not quantitative like prostate specific antigens (PSA).

2. Tumor-associated antigens (TAA), which are seen in normal cells in addition to cancer cells and are the result of mutations in the regulatory part of genes, which means that the amount of antigen production increases (over-expression), not that new antigens are produced. In other words, they are the result of quantitative changes in genes, such as CEA.

Clinical immunotherapy of cancer faces a number of challenges, including high toxicity of immune mediators, lack of effective and targeted delivery of cancer antigens to immune cells, and off-target side effects. Also, there are some limitations related to cancer immunotherapy, such as induction Destructive autoimmunity and lack of effective delivery of cancer antigens to immune cells.

In addition, the immunosuppressive property of the tumor microenvironment weakens the efficacy of cancer immunotherapy; For this reason, nanotechnology has been used in cancer immunotherapy to increase the efficiency of immunotherapy and overcome these limitations. Nanoparticles (NPs) have several unique properties such as small particle size, tunable structure and high cell penetration ability, and for this reason, nanotechnology provides an opportunity to overcome the shortcomings of previous cancer immunotherapy and thus increase its efficiency.

Nano particles are produced in both natural and artificial ways and have shown profound immunomodulatory effects (stimulating the immune system or suppressing the immune system) and therefore, they have been used to treat various types of diseases.

2. Material and Methods

In cancer immunotherapy, nanoparticles play a vital role in activating the host's immune system based on three different strategies of presenting antigens and adjuvants, presenting antigens and acting as a self-helper, and presenting or acting as adjuvants and inducing cell death.

Immune-suppressing nanoparticles have been used to treat inflammation and autoimmune diseases, while immune-stimulating nanoparticles have been used to treat cancer and some other infectious diseases.

In this article, we have mainly focused on the use of nanoparticles as a means of antigen delivery (immune stimulation). First, let's introduce a number of nano particles that stimulate the immune system, which are widely used in immunotherapy.

1. Polymeric Nanoparticles: These nanoparticles are the most widely used immune stimulants because they have excellent biocompatibility, biodegradability, solubility in water and high capacity to load components related to the immune system. D,L_lactic_coglycolic acid (PLGA), Poly glutamic acid (PGA), Poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLG), poly (ethylene glycol) (PEG), poly ethylenimine (PEI) and chitosan are commonly used polymeric nanoparticles in cancer immunotherapy. For example, subcutaneous administration of PLGA nanoformulation leads to its migration to lymph nodes where it subsequently activates dendritic cells (DCs) and CD8+ T cells; As a result, anti-cancer responses in bladder, melanoma and kidney carcinoma models are increased.

2. Liposomes: Liposomes have also emerged as an important nanoparticle and are used as a vehicle for the delivery of drugs, genes, and vaccines. Some examples of liposomal formulations include

DOTAP (1,2-dioleoyl-3-trimethylammonium-propane),

β - (N- [N',N'-dimethyl aminoethane] - carbamoyl) cholesterol (DC Chol) and dimethyl diocta decylammonium (DDA).

These liposomal formulations are used for effective delivery of antigens to antigen-presenting cells (APC) and also used as vaccine adjuvants, thereby increasing the antigen-specific immune response. pH-responsive dextran-modified liposomes are efficiently taken up by dendritic cells and deliver entrapped ovalbumin (OVA) to the cytosol. Cationic liposomes can effectively deliver synthetic long peptide antigens to dendritic cells and thus lead to the activation of CD8 + cytotoxic T cells. Hence, liposomes can be considered as an efficient delivery system for peptide-based cancer vaccines.

3. Gold nanoparticles: Gold nanoparticles (GNPs) are also used in immunotherapy due to their low toxicity, adjustable surface

chemistry, and easy shape and size control. GNPs are an important class of immunostimulating nanoparticles that show their response by activating macrophages and subsequent differentiation into dendritic-like cells, leading to T cell proliferation and cytokine release. It was also found that GNPs are useful as an aid for antibody production in mice, and their immunogenic properties increase further when they are used in combination with other immune stimulants such as CpG-ODNs. In addition, GNPs can prevent tumor growth by regulating the microenvironment surrounding the tumor.

4. Carbon nanotubes: Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) cause immune effects both in vitro and in vivo. All the studies that have been done have clearly shown that CNTs can be used as an immune system stimulating agent and also as a means of delivering antigens and adjuvants for cancer immunotherapy. For example, Dong et al. in 2019 used mannose-modified MWCNTs (oxidized multiwalled carbon nanotubes) to deliver tumor antigen OVA to dendritic cells. They observed that these nanovectors were rapidly taken up by dendritic cells and further increased dendritic maturation of cells and secretion of cytokines to generate strong antitumor immune responses.

5. Silica Nanoparticles: Silica Nanoparticles are mostly biocompatible and are widely used in various biomedical applications such as bioimaging, tumor targeting, and drug or vaccine delivery. Studies have shown that such nanovaccines induce both cell- and hormone-mediated immune responses without causing any cytotoxic effects at very low doses of antigens in mice; Therefore, it shows their self-help potential and biocompatibility in vaccine delivery programs. These nanoparticles reduce the level of intracellular glutathione (GSH) and increase the level of ROS (reactive oxygen species), which induces more strong responses of cytotoxic T cells (CD8+ T) and also improves antitumor activity.

6. Magnetic Nanoparticles: Currently, nanomagnetic particles are widely used in the field of theranostics due to their magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) properties. Among these nanoparticles, superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs) are more interested by many researchers for cancer theranostic applications.

Studies have shown that DMSA coated with SPIONs effectively delivers anti-tumor cytokines such as IFN- γ to the tumor site by using an external magnetic field, and as a result, effective nanoparticle aggregation and cytokine releasing in the tumor site leads to an increase in T cell population, macrophage infiltration, anti-angiogenesis, and tumor growth suppression. In addition, dextran-coated nano-magnetic particles that act with T-cell activating proteins have been identified and They increase the activation of T cells by using an external magnetic field and further inhibit tumor growth. Also, in another study, it was observed that the conjugate of OVA and silica covered with magnetic nanoparticles is effectively absorbed by dendritic cells and activates T Helper 1 cell response for specific antigens, as well as induces T CD8+ response for specific antigens.

7. protein Nanoparticles: Nano-protein particles have been effective as vaccines to deliver tumor antigens and adjuvants to

induce anti-tumor immune response. Biomimicking protein nanoparticles can effectively deliver peptide epitopes and CpG-ODNs that activate dendritic cells simultaneously, leading to the increase and long-term activity of T CD8+ cells, as well as enhancing antigen cross-presentation.

8. **Micelles:** Micelles have been used as a nano-antigen carrier to increase the potency of cancer vaccines. In a study, they used polymer hybrid micelles (PHMs) to encapsulate melanoma antigen peptides (Trp2) and TLR9 agonist (CpG-ODN) and observed that these nanovaccines can effectively target proximal lymph nodes. Also, these nanoparticles cause the entry of antigen in the dendritic cells. This co-delivery system stimulates more antigen-specific T CD8+ cell immune responses and induces a strong antitumor effect in a lung metastatic melanoma model. Nanovaccines produced with micelles further induce the maturation of Dendritic cells, cytokine secretion and increase antigen cross-presentation, which leads to the induction of antigen-specific immune response.

9. **Virus-like particles:** Virus-like particles (VLPs) have also been used as an ideal nanovaccine to enhance the efficacy of cancer immunotherapy. In a study, it was found that inhalation of self-assembled VLPs that derived from Cowpea mosaic virus (CPMV) significantly reduced B16F10 lung melanoma and induced a strong antitumor systemic immune response in mice by activating neutrophils in the tumor microenvironment. Also recently, Fogel and his colleagues reported that VLPs derived from CPMV virus induce strong anti-tumor immune response against intracranial glioma. Also, in another study, they encapsulated CpG-ODNs in CCMV virus-derived VLPs for targeted delivery of CpG-ODNs to tumor-associated macrophages in the tumor microenvironment and showed that VLPs loaded on CpG-ODNs effectively is absorbed by macrophages in the tumor microenvironment and induces more antitumor activity compared to free CpG-ODNs in both in vitro and in vivo conditions.

10. **Nanoemulsions:** Nanoemulsions (NEs) are used as adjuvants or antigen/adjuvant delivery vehicles to induce strong antitumor immune responses. In various studies, it was found that such nanovaccines effectively activate dendritic cells and induce the proliferation of antigen-specific T CD8+ cells and T CD4+ cells, as well as induce antibody and CD8+ T cell immune responses. the researchers encapsulated the E6 and E7 antigens of the papilloma virus, which causes cervical cancer, on Clec9A-TNE and showed that this combination significantly prevents tumor growth and increases the expression of IFN- γ .

11. **Nanogels:** In acquired immunity against cancers, dendritic cells, which are the most important APCs, present part of the tumor antigen to T Helper (T CD4+) and T Cytotoxic (T CD8+) lymphocytes to produce a strong response against That antigen. These nanogels are effectively absorbed by dendritic cells and activate them, thereby activating T lymphocytes. The main function of these nanogels is to activate dendritic cells. It was shown in the research that GDR/OVA nanovaccines significantly increase the maturation of dendritic cells, the absorption of antigen by dendritic cells and the release of cytosolic antigen. GDR (galactosyl dextran-retinal) nanogels also induce lysosomal

rupture in dendritic cells and facilitate ROS production, which further promotes cross-presentation by dendritic cells and generates a strong antitumor immune response.

12. **Dendrimers:** Dendrimer-based nanovaccines, like nanogels, are well absorbed by dendritic cells and induce an acquired immune response. For example, combined DGBA-OVA-CpG nanovaccines are effectively absorbed by dendritic cells and promote dendritic cell maturation and lysosomal escape, which further facilitate antigen cross-presentation by dendritic cells.

3. Result

The type of interaction between nanoparticles and antigens is very important for the effective delivery of antigens in order to protect the cargo molecules from enzymatic degradation and its premature release through the circulatory system. Antigen and adjuvant molecules are loaded on nano particles in three ways:

1. **Physical adsorption:** Adsorption of antigen or adjuvant molecules on the surface of nano particles is generally done through electrostatic interactions or hydrophobic interactions. This type of interaction is relatively weaker, which leads to the rapid separation and release of antigens inside the cell. This type of interaction is carried out by proper engineering of the surface of nanoparticles with suitable coating materials or functionalization. Such as BSA (bovine serum albumin) adsorption on FDU-12 silica nanoparticles, OVA antigen adsorption on amine functionalized MSNs (mesoporous silica nanoparticle) and non-covalent TAA (NY-ESO-1) adsorption as well as an adjuvant on MWCNTs surface.

2. **Encapsulation:** Encapsulation of antigens and adjuvants through nano-polymer particles is achieved simply by mixing antigens or adjuvants with polymer, followed by emulsification and solvent evaporation. Encapsulation leads to a relatively stronger connection of the cargo molecules inside the polymeric nanoparticles and the trapped molecules are released after being internalized in the cell, and subsequently, the destruction of the nanoparticles takes place, and the dendritic cells are effectively active. they become Such as simultaneous encapsulation of OVA antigen and poly (I:C) adjuvant inside PLGA nanoparticles for effective delivery to dendritic cells.

3. **Chemical combination:** the chemical combination of antigens and adjuvants with nanoparticles provides the strongest interactions; Therefore, it allows the slow release of antigens. In this type of interaction, the antigen is chemically attached to the surface of nanoparticles. Such as the chemical combination of OVA antigen and TMC (N-trimethyl chitosan) nanoparticles using a disulfide bond.

In order to induce antitumor immune responses, tumor antigens and adjuvants must be effectively delivered to APCs through a favorable interaction between nanocarriers and APCs because T CD4+ lymphocytes only respond to antigens presented by MHC-II molecules (these molecules are only on the surface of APCs) are delivered to them, they do not respond to any antigen, as a result of the interaction of nanocarriers with APCs such as dendritic cells, B lymphocytes, macrophages and Langerhans

cells in the skin are very important. Now let's examine the factors that affect this interaction:

1. Size: The size of nano particles is one of the important factors affecting its interaction with APCs located in lymph nodes. Nanoparticles come in three sizes: small (less than 5 nm), medium (between 5 and 100 nm), and large (more than 100 nm). Compared to larger nano particles, smaller nano particles enter the lymphatic network more easily and reach the lymph nodes, thus they work better. According to research conducted by various researchers, smaller nanoparticles are able to increase the entry of antigens of foreign origin in the cytosol while nanoparticles larger than 100 nm are not able. The antigen delivery efficiency of smaller nanoparticles is higher than larger nanoparticles and they better induce cytotoxic T lymphocyte responses.

2. Shape: According to the studies, immunological responses against nanoparticles clearly depend on the shape of the nanoparticles. In this way, the produced cytokines by the cells and the type of stimulated cells are different and depend on the shape of the nanoparticles.

3. Surface charge: It is generally known that the positive surface charge of nano particles induces the absorption of dendritic cells due to electrostatic interactions with the negative charge of the cell membrane, and as a result, they create a stronger immune response. For example, positively charged liposomes effectively transfer egg albumin to the cytoplasm of APCs and induce a greater antigen-mediated immune response compared to neutral and negatively charged liposomes due to increased interaction and subsequent uptake. Although cationic nanoparticles are suitable for cell internalization through electrostatic interactions, sometimes cationic nanoparticles can cause platelet aggregation and hemolysis or can disrupt membrane integrity.

4. Hydrophobicity: Hydrophobic polymeric nanoparticles induce a greater immune response compared to hydrophilic nanopolymer particles, and according to all studies, a linear increase in immune activity was observed with increasing hydrophobicity of nanoparticles.

5. Surface modification with ligands: Surface modification of nanoparticles with specific ligands is another important factor that increases targeted delivery of nanoparticles to APCs and thus prevents off-target side effects and improves antitumor immune response. For example, chitosan nanoparticles whose surface is covered with mannose, compared to chitosan nanoparticles whose surface is not covered with mannose, better deliver antigens to dendritic cells.

There are two very important things to know:

* APCs present antigens that come from outside the cell (exogenous) to T CD4+ lymphocytes by MHC class II molecules that they have on their surface.

* Antigens that are produced inside the cell (endogenous), such as antigens of tumor cells and infected cells with viruses, are presented to T CD8+ lymphocytes by the MHC class I molecule that is present on the surface of those cells.

In cancer, because APCs take the antigen from the outside (due to the necrosis of cancer cells), they present it to T CD4+ lymphocytes using MHC class II; But dendritic cells have a path called cross-presentation that can present exogenous antigens to T CD8+ cells on their MHC class I level.

This is the characteristic of dendritic cells, which are important cells in the defense against tumor cells. This type of antigen recognition causes T CD8+ cells to develop. T CD8+ cells that first encounter dendritic cells are called naive. These naive cells do not have lethal tools; When they encounter antigens, they increase first, but they cannot do anything. Then, through cytokines of T helper cells, for example interferon gamma, they mature and make CTLs.

Now these cells have lethal factors and these cells enter the blood circulation and destroy tumor cells. Every body cell that becomes a tumor has its own MHC class I that presents its endogenous antigen on its surface, and the cytotoxic cell recognizes it in this way and destroys that tumor cell. According to these explanations, antigen delivery by dendritic cells is very important in immunotherapy, and nanoparticles can help us a lot in this direction for the targeted delivery of nanoparticles. These days, researchers' attention has been drawn to immune-stimulating nanoparticles that can be effectively internalized by APCs; As a result, the efficiency of cancer antigen delivery to the target cells is increased and the antigen-specific immune response starts and the reprogramming of the microenvironment surrounding the tumor is carried out. In addition to this targeted delivery, nanoparticles can also protect the cargo molecules from losing biological activity during circulation and prevent off-target side effects.

The most important immune cells in dealing with cancer cells are dendritic cells, T lymphocytes and natural killer cells. Now we want to talk about how to stimulate them in immunotherapy by using nanoparticles.

1. Stimulation of dendritic cells: Dendritic cells are the most important APCs and originate from the bone marrow and are divided into two categories: myeloid DCs (mDCs) and plasmacytoid DCs (pDCs). Dendritic cells express both MHC-I and MHC-II molecules and present antigens to T cell receptors to activate T CD8+ cells and T CD4+ cells, respectively. Dendritic cells have TLRs that play an important role in both innate and acquired immune responses by recognizing intracellular and extracellular pathogens. Activation of TLR signaling pathways facilitates the acquired immune response by producing cytokines, chemokines and MHC molecules. Delivery of tumor-associated antigens to T lymphocytes is necessary to stimulate them and perform immunotherapy. There are two methods for delivering antigens by dendritic cells with the help of nanoparticles;

1) In the first method, bounded nanoparticles with antigens enter the cytosol of dendritic cells through endocytosis, but the endosome is not released in the cytosol, and as a result, dendritic cells deliver TAA antigens to T helper lymphocytes through MHC-II. Then this type of T lymphocytes activates cytotoxic T lymphocytes.

2) In the second method, conjugation of nanoparticles with antigens are released in the dendritic cytosol of the cells, and in fact, they are endogenous antigens, and for this reason, MHC-I that is located on the surface of dendritic cells directly activates cytotoxic T lymphocytes. TLRs are receptors that have different types. Some TLRs are expressed on the surface of the cell membrane, and some are inside the cytoplasm, which are expressed on the membrane of endosomes. In the second method that T cells are directly activated, nanovaccines should be bounded with the specific ligands of TLRs on the surface of the plasma membrane and the specific ligands of intracellular TLRs. as a result, they act as an adjuvant for stimulation of dendritic cells and activation of T cells and in this way facilitate immunotherapy.

2. Stimulation of T lymphocytes: To explain how to stimulate T lymphocytes, we first explain a topic called self-tolerance. self-tolerance means tolerance to self-antigens. We expect that the immune system will not respond to self-antigens and that the immune response will only occur against non-self-antigens. If these mechanisms become dysfunctional, an immune response against self-antigens will occur and an autoimmune disease will develop. When a foreign antigen such as a microbial antigen enters the body, lymphocytes multiply and differentiate and an immune response is created; But due to the self-tolerance mechanism, no immune response is created against self-antigens.

In fact, one of the most important features of the specific immune response is non-responsiveness to self-antigens. A very important point is that tolerance is related to B and T lymphocytes and it is an antigen-specific mechanism and innate immunity does not visited with tolerance. In the discussion of cancer treatment, cancer cells abuse the tolerance mechanism and cause immune responses to be turned off. So, by knowing and overcoming the mechanisms of tolerance, it is possible to prevent the escape of cancer cells from the immune system and cure cancer. In general, we can say that wherever tolerance benefits the body, it should be strengthened and wherever it is harmful to the body, it should be restricted for therapeutic purposes.

As it was said, following the presenting of antigen by APCs to the receptors of T lymphocytes, they are activated and become executive lymphocytes and cause the destruction of the pathogen. We have a group of T lymphocytes called regulatory T lymphocytes whose job is to inhibit immune responses. One of the most important mechanisms of regulatory T lymphocytes to inhibit the immune response is the expression of the CD25 molecule. CD25 is IL-2 receptor with high affinity; Therefore, they absorb the IL-2s that exist in the environment and can activate T lymphocytes to their surface and do not allow them to be available to T lymphocytes. One of the most important molecules that regulatory T lymphocytes have on their surface is CTLA-4.

CD28 is present on the surface of T cells that want to be activated, and CD28 binds to CD80 and CD86 on the surface of APCs to receive the co-stimulatory signal. CTLA-4 also binds to CD80 and CD86. In fact, the role of CTLA-4 is to compete with CD28 to bind to CD80 and CD86. Because the affinity of CTLA-4 is higher, it wins the competition and binds to the co-stimulatory

signals and removes them from the access of the T cells that want to be activated, and in this way the response of T cells is restricted by T lymphocytes. To treat cancer, we can prevent the growth of tumor cells by controlling immuno suppression processes; As mentioned, there is a CTLA-4 molecule on the surface of regulatory T lymphocytes, which has the opposite function of the CD28 molecule and controls the immune response, that is why they are called immune checkpoint. Now, by producing antibodies against these molecules, we can inhibit their activity and intensify the response of the immune system against cancer cells. For this reason, these antibodies are called immune checkpoint blockers. Other immune checkpoint molecules include PD1 and PD-L1.

With these given explanations about T lymphocytes, we can now better address how they are stimulated with the help of nanoparticles. There are two ways to stimulate T lymphocytes:

1) T cells are separated from the tumor tissue of a cancer patient and form a colony of them, and then those same cells are entered into the patient's body.

2) the design of Nanovaccine to activate tumor-specific T CD8+ lymphocytes.

In both cases, artificial APCs (aAPCs) are required to mimic antigen presentation as well as T cell activation with the capacity of natural APCs. Several nanoformulations including liposomes, magnetic beads, paramagnetic nanoparticles, and biodegradable polymers have been designed to synthesize aAPCs to directly activate T cells.

Essential signals required for T cell activation by aAPCs:

1) co-stimulatory signals such as anti-CD3 and CD28 antibodies.

2) MHC-I peptide molecules.

Finally, these nanoparticle-based aAPCs activate T cells according to the described processes and prevent inactivating of them by combining with immune checkpoint blocker antibodies such as anti-PD1 and anti-CTLA-4 antibodies.

3. Stimulation of natural killer cells: NK cells are the part of the cells of the innate immune system. Anywhere in the body, when cancer cells begin to proliferate, the innate immune system first deals with them. The main innate immune cells that play a role in responding to cancer cells are NK cells. NK cells quickly recognize cancer cells and deal with them. a part of tumor antigens are released either by NK cells or by the necrosis of cancer tissues, and finally carried to secondary lymphatic organs by APC cells, especially dendritic cells. In secondary lymph nodes, APCs present these antigens to T CD4+ lymphocytes and thus a specific immune response start.

NK cells have two types of receptors:

1. Inhibitory receptor: including immunoglobulin-like inhibitory receptors

2. Activating receptor: CD16, natural cytotoxicity receptors (NCR), LY49

Inhibitory receptors of NK cells binds with MHC class I of body cells and checks them. If they do not have any problems, they do not cause their death. NK cells play a very important role in destroying infected cells with virus and tumor cells, especially tumor cells of blood origin and cells that have decreased MHC class I expression. One of the mechanisms of viruses and tumor cells for escaping the immune system is reducing the expression of MHC-I on their surface and so that they are not recognized by NK cells; to counter with this mechanism, NK cells use their activating receptors to destroy those cells. The function of NK cells is releasing the contents of their granules; including perforin, granzyme and granulysin on the surface of target cell and then destroy the target cell. NK cells are also able to perform the ADCC process in such a way that tumor antigens bind to the Fab part of the IgG class antibody, and NK cells also have the Fc γ RIIIa receptor on their surface, which binds to the Fc part of the IgG class antibody. In this way, they are activated and release their own granules on the surface of tumor cells and cause the destruction of tumor cells through apoptosis, and finally NK cells act as an adjuvant for specific immunity.

According to the explanations, we will discuss about the immunotherapy with targeting these cells by the help of nanoparticles. For example, nanographene sheets bound with anti-CD16 antibody target the CD16 receptor of NK cells and thus lead to their activation.

Delivery of genes that encode activating receptors of NK cells and pro-inflammatory cytokines to NK cells through nanoparticles can stimulate the activation of NK cells and thus improve cancer immunotherapy. Also, under the influence of IL-2 and IL-12 cytokines, NK cells become LAK (Lymphokine Activated killer) cells, which have a great ability to destroy tumor cells; So, if we deliver the encoding genes of IL-12 and IL-2 cytokines to NK cells with the help of nanoparticles, these cells will increase the amount of these two cytokines in the serum and destroy tumor cells.

In the advanced stages of cancer, every cell that enters the microenvironment of the tumor, serves the tumor and somehow loses its properties, for example, macrophages become type 2 macrophages and T helper cells become T regulatory. A series of other regulatory cells, such as MDSC or inhibitory cells of myeloid origin, appear in the tumor environment. All of these cells cause that tumor cells escape from the immune system.

Other mechanisms that play a role in the escape of tumor cells, including:

1. the loss of antigens or lack of expression of antigens.
2. the reduction of MHC class I expression that makes T CD8+ cells unable to recognize tumor cells.
3. the production of immuno suppressive molecules such as TGF- β (which causes the production of regulatory T), MMP (matrix metalloproteinase), galectin-3 and osteopontin. these proteins are responsible for the

production of extracellular matrix and provide an favorable environment for tumor to grow.

4. The production of an enzyme called IDO by tumor cells and MDSC cells, which breaks down the tryptophan and arginine. These amino-acids are necessary for the proliferation.

One of the strategies in Anticancer immunotherapy is the regulation of TME by nanoparticles. Nanoparticles should be designed in such a way that they can respond to the biochemical differences between the tumor and surrounding tissue of the tumor. and thus selectively deliver immunostimulants to the target cells in the microenvironment surrounding the tumor.

Different strategies include:

- 1) Production of responsive nanoparticles to hypoxia.
- 2) Placing PH-sensitive substances in nanoparticles.
- 3) increasing permeability and retention effect (EPR) by controlling the size of nano particles
- 4) Placing the substrate for metalloproteinase enzymes (MMPs) inside the tumor.

In the tumor microenvironment, regulatory T cells suppress the immune response by stopping the function of APC and preventing the activation and proliferation of T cells. Therefore, by suppressing the function of regulatory T cells with the help of nanoparticles, antitumor immunity can be restored. For example, anti-CD25 antibodies, which are the ligand of CD25 on the surface of regulatory T cells, can be directed to the tumor microenvironment with the help of nanoparticles, and these antibodies inhibit T regulatory cells and activate T CD8+ cells. they become Another strategy to inhibit the function of T regulatory cells is the use of anti-CTLA-4 antibodies, which bind as ligands to the CTLA-4 receptor present on the surface of regulatory T cells and prevent their function. MDSCs are also a type of regulatory cells with inhibitory function, so removing them from the tumor microenvironment with the help of nanoparticles can improve the efficiency of cancer immunotherapy.

There are two types of macrophages; M1 and M2, M1 macrophages activate immune responses and M2 macrophages have an inhibitory function. The macrophages in the tumor microenvironment are of M2 type, and if these macrophages are changed to M1 macrophages, the performance of cancer immunotherapy will improve. In the conducted studies, it has been observed that exosomes derived from M1 macrophages and nanovesicles derived from those exosomes can change M2 macrophages to M1 type macrophages and cause T CD8+ response and thus reduce tumor progression. as mentioned, the tryptophan and arginine are necessary for the proliferation of T cells, and the IDO enzyme breaks down these amino acids and prevents the proliferation of T cells; With the help of nanoparticles, NLG919 (IDO inhibitor) can be directed to the tumor to inhibit the IDO enzyme.

4. Conclusion

Tumor cells secrete several cytokines and other factors that act as immunosuppressors and block the activity of tumor infiltrating lymphocytes (TIL). Therefore, targeting those suppression pathways can increase antitumor efficacy. For example, the STAT3 signaling pathway promotes tumor growth by inducing hypoxia and angiogenesis, increasing MMPs, and by promoting the secretion of immunosuppressive cytokines. Therefore, it has been shown that the delivery of STAT3-siRNA through nanoparticles disrupts the STAT3 pathway and prevents the production of immunosuppressive cytokines. Similarly, delivery of TGF- β -siRNA via nanoparticles showed reduced number of regulatory T cells and increased T CD8+ responses.

Finally, it can be said that immunotherapy by using nanoparticles has undergone rapid development and is considered as a potential therapeutic strategy for cancer treatment. Nano particles can target immune cells well and also have the ability to simultaneously deliver antigen and adjuvant to APCs, thus increasing the efficiency of cancer immunotherapy. Nanoparticles allow higher cellular uptake of immunostimulating

agents to induce B and T cell immune responses and sometimes nanoparticles act as a self-help. Because nanoparticles interact with the immune system, their immunotoxicity must be evaluated correctly. Some nanoparticles also change the intracellular signaling pathway; Therefore, this criterion should be considered when the toxicity of nanoparticles is evaluated. Sometimes, the immune system recognizes nanoparticles as foreign substances when they interact with serum proteins, and an autoimmunity against nanoparticles is created. Therefore, for successful clinical application, nanoparticles must be designed in such a way that they cannot cause hypersensitivity or allergic sensitization and are easily cleared from the body.

These days, most researchers working in the field of immunostimulating nanoparticles try to formulate nanoparticles derived from nature because they are much safer and more biocompatible than others, but they also require careful consideration about their interactions with various biological components, including immune cells. In general, immunostimulating nanoparticles for cancer treatment is a promising research field and the design of safer nanovaccines is in favor of cancer patients.

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